

Triterpenes and Sterols from *Sonneratia alba*

Consolacion Y Ragasa^{1,2,*}, Virgilio D. Ebajo Jr.², Mariquit M. De Los Reyes^{3,4}, Emelina H Mandia⁴, Robert Brkljača⁵, Sylvia Urban⁵

¹Chemistry Department, De La Salle University Science & Technology Complex Leandro V. Locsin Campus, Biñan City, Laguna 4024, Philippines

²Chemistry Department, De La Salle University, 2401 Taft Avenue, Manila 1004, Philippines

³Biology Department, De La Salle University Science & Technology Complex Leandro V. Locsin Campus, Biñan City, Laguna 4024, Philippines

⁴Biology Department, De La Salle University, 2401 Taft Avenue, Manila 1004, Philippines

⁵School of Applied Sciences (Discipline of Chemistry), RMIT University (City Campus), Melbourne 3001, Victoria, Australia

Available Online: 23rd October, 2015

ABSTRACT

Chemical investigation of the dichloromethane extract of *Sonneratia alba* Sm. afforded mixtures of oleanolic acid (**1a**) and ursolic acid (**1b**), α -amyirin cinnamate (**2a**) and β -amyirin cinnamate (**2b**), and β -sitosterol (**3a**) and stigmasterol (**3b**) from the fruit; lupeol (**4**), and mixtures of **1a** and **1b**, and **3a** and **3b** from the twigs; and **1b** and squalene (**5**) from the leaves. The structures of **1-5** were identified by comparison of their NMR data with literature data.

Keywords: *Sonneratia alba*, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid, α -amyirin cinnamate, β -amyirin cinnamate, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, lupeol, squalene

INTRODUCTION

Sonneratia alba J.E. Sm., of the family Sonneratiaceae (APG Lythraceae), is commonly known as mangrove apple, and is considered as the most widespread of all mangrove trees, abundant in East Africa, Southeast Asia, Northern Australia, Borneo, and the Pacific Islands¹. It is a medium-sized tree, found in low-intertidal zones, growing along seashores and at the mouth of tidal creeks on sandy, rocky or muddy soils, and also on coral terraces^{2,3}. *S. alba* has many commercial applications⁴. It is widely used for firewood and construction, often timbered for making ribs for boats, house materials and flooring, and bridges and wharfs. The pneumatophores of this species are used to produce cork and floats. In India and Indonesia, the fruit is used to make a beverage. In other Malay regions, the fruit is eaten ripe, while the leaves are eaten either raw or cooked⁵. *S. alba* is also used in traditional medicine as a compress for swellings and sprains⁴. The leaves, trunk and bark exhibits antioxidant properties⁶, while the sepal shows antioxidant and anti-lipid peroxidation properties⁷. A number of studies have been conducted on the chemical constituents and biological activities of *S. alba*. 3 β -Hydroxy-lup-9(11),12-diene, 28-oic acid, lupeol and lupan-3 β -ol which were isolated from the bark of *S. alba* exhibited antibacterial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and *Streptococcus mutans* ATCC 25175, with minimum inhibitory concentrations ranging from 15-33 to 35-55 μ g/mL, respectively⁸. Furthermore,

lupan-3 β -ol and lupeol isolated from the bark of *S. alba* displays antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus* and *S. mutans* with MIC values of 94.1 and 120; and 35.2 and 22.6 mg/mL, respectively⁹. Moreover, the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of *S. alba* yielded oleanolic acid, betulin, betulinic acid, aliphatic acid, methyl gallate and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural¹⁰. In another study, the CHCl₃ and aqueous soluble fractions of *S. alba* showed significant free radical scavenging activity with IC₅₀ values of 15.58 \pm 0.55 μ g/mL and 15.06 \pm 0.35 μ g/mL, respectively. At a concentration of 400 μ g/disc, the CCl₄, CHCl₃ and aqueous soluble fractions inhibited bacterial growth with zone of inhibitions ranging from 7-9 mm, 7-10 mm and 7 mm, respectively. The CCl₄ soluble fraction also showed cytotoxic activity with an LC₅₀ value of 7.94 \pm 0.450 μ g/mL. These extracts yielded lupeol, oleanolic acid, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and sitost-4-en-3-one¹¹. Lupeol, oleanolic acid, betulinic acid, 2,6-dimethoxy-*p*-benzoquinone, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol were isolated from the twigs of *S. alba*. Lupeol and betulinic acid exhibited antimycobacterial activity with MIC values of 25 and 50 mg/mL respectively. 2,6-Dimethoxy-*p*-benzoquinone showed antimalarial activity against *P. falciparum* with an IC₅₀ value of 3.08 mg/mL¹². In another study, 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic acid from *S. alba* was reported to exhibit a stronger antioxidant activity than the ascorbic acid standard with IC₅₀ values of 11.35 and 17.64 μ g/mL, respectively¹³. Moreover, the gamma linolenic

acid (GLA) percentage in the leaves of *S. alba* was reported as 36.20%, while in the stem it was 11%¹⁴. In this study, the dichloromethane extracts of the different parts of *S. alba* afforded mixtures of oleanolic acid (**1a**) and ursolic acid (**1b**) in a 3:1 ratio, α -amyrin cinnamate (**2a**) and β -amyrin cinnamate (**2b**) in a 1:3 ratio, and β -sitosterol (**3a**) and stigmasterol (**3b**) in a 3:1 ratio from the fruit; lupeol (**4**), and mixtures of **1a** and **1b** in a 1:3 ratio, and **3a** and **3b** in a 3:1 ratio from the twigs; and **1b** and squalene (**5**) from the leaves. The structures of **1-5** are presented in Fig. 1. To the best of our knowledge this is the first report on the isolation of **1b**, **2a**, **2b**, and **5** from *S. alba*.

MATERIALS AD METHODS

General Experimental Procedure

¹H (500 MHz) and ¹³C (125 MHz) NMR spectra were acquired in CDCl₃ on a 500 MHz Agilent DD2 NMR spectrometer with referencing to solvent signals (δ 7.26 and 77.0 ppm). Column chromatography was performed with silica gel 60 (70-230 mesh). Thin layer chromatography was performed with plastic backed plates coated with silica gel F₂₅₄ and the plates were visualized by spraying with vanillin/H₂SO₄ solution followed by warming.

Sample Collection

Samples of fruits, leaves and twigs of *Sonneratia alba* were collected from the De La Salle University – Bro Alfred Shields FSC Ocean Research (SHORE) Center in Matuod, Lian, Batangas in April 2014. The sample was authenticated by one of the authors (EHM) and deposited at De La Salle University Herbarium with voucher specimen #924.

General Isolation Procedure

A glass column 18 inches in height and 1.0 inch internal diameter was packed with silica gel. The crude extracts were fractionated by silica gel chromatography using increasing proportions of acetone in CH₂Cl₂ (10% increment) as eluents. Fifty milliliter fractions were collected. All fractions were monitored by thin layer chromatography. Fractions with spots of the same R_f values were combined and rechromatographed in appropriate solvent systems until TLC pure isolates were obtained. A glass column 12 inches in height and 0.5 inch internal diameter was used for the rechromatography. Two milliliter fractions were collected. Final purifications were conducted using Pasteur pipettes as columns. One milliliter fractions were collected.

Isolation of the chemical constituents of the fruits

The freeze-dried fruits of *S. alba* (140.0 g) were ground in a blender, soaked in CH₂Cl₂ for 3 days and then filtered. The solvent was evaporated under vacuum to afford a crude extract (0.70 g) which was chromatographed using increasing proportions of acetone in CH₂Cl₂ at 10% increment. The 20% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ fraction was rechromatographed (3 \times) using 5% EtOAc in petroleum ether to afford a mixture of **2a** and **2b** (4 mg) after washing with petroleum ether. The 30% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ fraction was rechromatographed (3 \times) using 15% EtOAc in petroleum ether to afford a mixture of **3a** and **3b** (5 mg) after washing with petroleum ether. The 60% to 80%

acetone in CH₂Cl₂ fractions were combined and rechromatographed (3 \times) using CH₃CN:Et₂O:CH₂Cl₂ (1.5:1.5:7, v/v) to yield a mixture of **1a** and **1b** (3 mg) after trituration with petroleum ether.

Isolation of the chemical constituents of the twigs

The air-dried twigs of *S. alba* (113.4 g) were ground in a blender, soaked in CH₂Cl₂ for 3 days and then filtered. The solvent was evaporated under vacuum to afford a crude extract (0.5 g) which was chromatographed using increasing proportions of acetone in CH₂Cl₂ at 10% increment. The 30% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ fraction was rechromatographed (2 \times) using 15% EtOAc in petroleum ether to afford **4** (5 mg) after washing with petroleum ether. The 40% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ was rechromatographed using 15% EtOAc in petroleum ether to afford a mixture of **3a** and **3b** (3 mg) after washing with petroleum ether. The 70% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ was rechromatographed (3 \times) using CH₃CN:Et₂O:CH₂Cl₂ (1:1:8, v/v) to yield a mixture of **1a** and **1b** (2 mg) after trituration with petroleum ether.

Isolation of the chemical constituents of the leaves

The air-dried leaves of *S. alba* (309.5 g) were ground in a blender, soaked in CH₂Cl₂ for 3 days and then filtered. The solvent was evaporated under vacuum to afford a crude extract (11 g) which was chromatographed using increasing proportions of acetone in CH₂Cl₂ at 10% increment. The CH₂Cl₂ fraction was rechromatographed (2 \times) using petroleum ether to afford **5** (10 mg). The 40% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ was rechromatographed using 15% EtOAc in petroleum ether to afford a mixture of **3a** and **3b** (3 mg) after washing with petroleum ether. The 70% acetone in CH₂Cl₂ was rechromatographed (3 \times) using CH₃CN:Et₂O:CH₂Cl₂ (1:1:8, v/v) to yield **1b** (5 mg) after trituration with petroleum ether.

Oleanolic acid (1a): ¹HNMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ 3.20 (dd, J = 10.0, 4.5 Hz, H-3 α), 5.27 (t, J = 3.5 Hz, H-12), 2.81 (dd, J = 4.2, 13.8 Hz, H-18), 1.15 (s, Me-27), 0.97 (s, Me-23), 0.91 (s, Me-25), 0.92 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, Me-30), 0.75 (s, Me-26), 0.76 (s, Me-24), 0.88 (J = 6.5 Hz, Me-29); ¹³CNMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz): δ 38.4 (C-1), 27.2 (C-2), 79.0 (C-3), 38.4 (C-4), 55.2 (C-5), 18.3 (C-6), 32.6 (C-7), 39.3 (C-8), 47.6 (C-9), 37.1 (C-10), 23.0 (C-11), 122.5 (C-12), 143.7 (C-13), 41.6 (C-14), 27.7 (C-15), 23.4 (C-16), 46.5 (C-17), 41.1 (C-18), 45.9 (C-19), 30.7 (C-20), 23.6 (C-21), 32.4 (C-22), 28.1 (C-23), 15.5 (C-24), 15.33 (C-25), 17.0 (C-26), 25.9 (C-27), 182.3 (C-28), 33.1 (C-29), 23.8 (C-30).

Ursolic acid (1b): ¹HNMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ 3.20 (dd, J = 10.0, 4.5 Hz, H-3 α), 5.23 (t, J = 3.5 Hz, H-12), 2.18 (1H, d, J = 11.4 Hz, H-18), 1.07 (s, Me-23), 0.81 (s, Me-24), 0.94 (s, Me-25), 0.86 (s, Me-26), 1.20 (s, Me-27), 0.80 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, Me-29), 0.91 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, Me-30); ¹³CNMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz): δ 38.5 (C-1), 27.2 (C-2), 79.0 (C-3), 38.5 (C-4), 55.2 (C-5), 18.3 (C-6), 33.1 (C-7), 39.5 (C-8), 47.5 (C-9), 37.1 (C-10), 23.6 (C-11), 125.8 (C-12), 138.0 (C-13), 42.0 (C-14), 29.4 (C-15), 23.4 (C-16), 47.9 (C-17), 52.5 (C-18), 30.7 (C-19), 30.6 (C-20), 27.2 (C-21), 37.0 (C-22), 24.2 (C-23), 15.4 (C-24), 15.6 (C-25), 17.0 (C-26), 24.2 (C-27), 177.5 (C-28), 22.7 (C-29), 24.1 (C-30).

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of oleanolic acid (**1a**), ursolic acid (**1b**), α -amyrin cinnamate (**2a**), β -amyrin cinnamate (**2b**), β -sitosterol (**3a**), stigmasterol (**3b**), lupeol (**4**), and squalene (**5**) from *Sonneratia alba*.

α -Amyrin cinnamate (2a): ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.65 (dd, J = 6.0, 10.1 Hz, H-3), 5.13 (t, J = 3.8 Hz, H-12), 0.92 (s, Me-23), 0.95 (s, Me-24), 1.01 (s, Me-25), 1.03 (s, Me-26), 1.08 (s, Me-27), 0.80 (s, Me-28), 0.80 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, Me-29), 0.92 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, Me-30), 7.67 (d, J = 16.0 Hz, H-2'), 6.44 (d, J = 16.0 Hz, H-3'), 7.53 (H-5', H-9'), 7.38 (H-6', H-8'), 7.38 (H-7').

β -Amyrin cinnamate (2b): ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.63 (t, J = 6.0 Hz, H-3), 5.17 (t, J = 3.7 Hz, H-12), 0.90

(s, Me-23), 0.93 (s, Me-24), 0.97 (s, Me-25), 0.96 (s, Me-26), 1.13 (s, Me-27), 0.82 (s, Me-28), 0.86 (s, Me-29), 0.85 (s, Me-30), 7.65 (d, J = 16.0 Hz, H-2'), 6.43 (d, J = 16.0 Hz, H-3'), 7.53 (H-5', H-9'), 7.37 (H-6', H-8'), 7.37 (H-7').

β -Sitosterol (3a): ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.50 (m, H-3), 5.35 (d, 4.8, H-5), 0.66 (s, Me-18), 0.99 (s, Me-19), 0.93 (d, 6.6, Me-21), 0.84 (d, J = 6.6, Me-26), 0.83 (d, J = 6.0, Me-27), 0.86 (t, J = 6.0, Me-29).

Stigmasterol (3b): ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 3.50 (m, H-3), 5.33 (d, $J = 4.8$, H-5), 0.68 (s, Me-18), 0.99 (s, Me-19), 1.01 (d, $J = 6.6$, Me-21), 5.13 (dd, $J = 8.4$, 15.6 Hz, H-22), 5.00 (dd, $J = 8.4$, 15.0 Hz, H-23), 0.84 (d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Me-26), 0.83 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, Me-27), 0.80 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, Me-29).

Lupeol (4): ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (CDCl_3 , 500 MHz) δ 4.68 (H-29b), 4.55 (H-29a), 3.18 (H-3), 1.68 (s, H₃-30), 0.96 (s, H₃-23), 0.78 (s, H₃-24), 0.83 (s, H₃-25), 0.94 (s, H₃-26), 1.06 (s, H₃-27), 0.91 (s, H₃-28), 1.68 (s, H₃-30).

Squalene (5): ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 5.08-5.13 (6H, =CH), 1.58 (18H, allylic Me, *cis*), 1.66 (6H, allylic Me, *trans*), 1.94-2.07 (20H, allylic CH_2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Silica gel chromatography of the dichloromethane extract of the fruits of *S. alba* afforded oleanolic acid (**1a**)¹⁵, ursolic acid (**1a**)¹⁶, α -amyrin cinnamate (**2a**)¹⁷, β -amyrin cinnamate (**2b**)¹⁷, β -sitosterol (**3a**)¹⁸, stigmasterol (**3b**)¹⁸, lupeol (**4**)¹⁹, and squalene (**5**)²⁰. The structures of **1-5** were identified by comparison of their NMR data with literature data. The 3:1 ratio of oleanolic acid (**1a**) and ursolic acid (**1b**) from the fruit and the 1:3 ratio of **1a** and **1b** from the twigs were deduced from the intensity of the ^1H NMR resonances for the olefinic protons²¹ at δ 5.27 for **1a** and δ 5.23 for **1b** and the allylic methine protons²¹ at δ 2.81 for **1a** and δ 2.18 for **1b**. The α -amyrin cinnamate (**2a**) and β -amyrin cinnamate (**2b**) in a 1:3 ratio was deduced from the intensities of the ^1H NMR resonances for the olefinic protons¹⁷ at δ 5.13 for **1a** and δ 5.17 for **1b**. The 3:1 ratio of the mixture of β -sitosterol (**3a**) and stigmasterol (**3b**) from the fruit and twigs was deduced from the intensities of the ^1H NMR resonances for the olefinic protons²² of **3a** at δ 5.33 and **3b** at δ 5.33, 5.13 and 5.00. Although bioassays were not conducted on the isolated compounds (**1-5**), there were previous studies that reported on their biological activities. Oleanolic acid (**1a**) was found to be anti-mutagenic and anti-tumor, inhibiting proliferation of gastric, colon, and liver cancer cells by inducing apoptosis and necrosis²³. Triterpene **1a** was found to inhibit mouse skin tumor²⁴ and exhibited significant anti-tumor activity against human colon carcinoma cell line HCT 15²⁵. A recent study identified **1a** as an anti-tumor compound able to suppress aerobic glycolysis in MCF-7 breast cancer cells by inducing a metabolic switch in the PKM2 to PKM1 ratio which is important in cancer development²⁶. A study reported that ursolic acid (**1b**) induced apoptosis in tumor cells by activation of caspases and modulation of pathways affecting cell proliferation and migration²⁷. It also decreased proliferation and induced apoptosis in gastric cancer cell line BGC-803 and hepatocellular cancer cell H22 xenograft, both *in vivo* and *in vitro*²⁸. Triterpene **1b** exhibited anti-tumor activity against human colon carcinoma cell line HCT15²⁵ and inhibited the growth of colon cancer-initiating cells by targeting STAT3²⁹. Triterpene **1b** showed anti-estrogenic effects suggesting its potential use as therapeutic agents against estrogen-dependent tumors³⁰. It has potential therapeutic use against prostate cancer through its anti-proliferative and

apoptotic effects³¹. A recent study reported that **1b** inhibited cell growth and proliferation of Jurkat leukemic T-cells, inhibiting PMA/PHA induced IL-2 and TNF- α production in a concentration and time dependent manner³². A study on cervical cancer cells TC-1 reported that ursolic acid-activated autophagy induced cytotoxicity and reduced tumor growth in a concentration-dependent manner³³. Another study evaluated the antitumor activities of **1b** on U87MG brain cancer cells and found that both G1-phase arrest and autophagy were induced by the compound³⁴. Compound **3a** and baicalein inhibited the proliferation of MCF-7 breast cancer cells induced by PhIP³⁵. A study reported that α -amyrin cinnamate (**2a**) and β -amyrin cinnamate (**2b**) inhibited inflammation with 50% inhibitory dose (ID_{50}) of 0.61 and 0.75 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{ear}$. Triterpenes **2a** and **2b** also induced Epstein-Barr virus early antigen with IC_{50} values of 401 and 405 mole ratio/32 pmol TPA, respectively¹⁷. β -Sitosterol (**3a**) was observed to have growth inhibitory effects on human breast MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 adenocarcinoma cells³⁶. It was shown to be effective for the treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia³⁷. It was also reported to attenuate β -catenin and PCNA expression, as well as quench radical *in vitro*, making it a potential anticancer drug for colon carcinogenesis³⁸. It can inhibit the expression of NPC1L1 in the enterocytes to reduce intestinal cholesterol uptake³⁹. It was reported to induce apoptosis mediated by the activation of ERK and the downregulation of Akt in MCA-102 murine fibrosarcoma cells⁴⁰. Stigmasterol (**3b**) shows therapeutic efficacy against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma bearing mice while conferring protection against cancer induced altered physiological conditions⁴¹. It lowers plasma cholesterol levels, inhibits intestinal cholesterol and plant sterol absorption, and suppresses hepatic cholesterol and classic bile acid synthesis in Wistar as well as WKY rats⁴². Other studies reported that stigmasterol showed cytostatic activity against Hep-2 and McCoy cells⁴³, markedly inhibited tumour promotion in two stage carcinogenesis experiments⁴⁴, exhibited antimutagenic⁴⁵, topical anti-inflammatory⁴⁶, antiosteoarthritic⁴⁷ and antioxidant⁴⁸ activities. Lupeol (**4**) exhibited antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory activities⁴⁹. It exhibited antiurolithiatic and diuretic activity⁵⁰. It prevented the formation of vesical calculi and reduced the size of the preformed stones in rats⁵¹. Squalene (**5**) was reported to significantly suppress colonic ACF formation and crypt multiplicity which strengthened the hypothesis that it possesses chemopreventive activity against colon carcinogenesis⁵². It showed cardioprotective effect which is related to inhibition of lipid accumulation by its hypolipidemic properties and/or its antioxidant properties⁵³. A recent study reported that tocotrienols, carotenoids, squalene and coenzyme Q10 have anti-proliferative effects on breast cancer cells⁵⁴. The preventive and therapeutic potential of squalene containing compounds on tumour promotion and regression have been reported⁵⁵. A recent review on the bioactivities of squalene has been provided⁵⁶.

CONCLUSION

S. alba is used in traditional medicine as a compress for swellings and sprains, hence it has anti-inflammatory activity. The leaves, trunk and bark were reported to exhibit antioxidant properties, while the sepal showed antioxidant and anti-lipid peroxidation properties. The triterpenes (**1a-1b**, **4-6**) and sterols (**3a** and **3b**) which were obtained from the different parts of *S. alba* were reported to exhibit anti-oxidant and anticancer properties. Furthermore, **2a**, **2b**, **3b** and **5** were reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory properties. Thus, the anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties of *S. alba* may be partly attributed to the synergistic effects of **1-5** which were obtained from the different parts of the mangrove.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

A research grant from the De La Salle University Science Foundation through the University Research Coordination Office is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- Mangrove Apple. *Sonneratia alba*. <http://www.naturia.per.sg/buloh/plants/sonneratia.htm> Downloaded on August 22, 2015.
- Sonneratia alba* (Mangrove Apple). [https://taxo4254.wikispaces.com/Sonneratia+alba+\(Mangrove+Apple\)](https://taxo4254.wikispaces.com/Sonneratia+alba+(Mangrove+Apple)). Downloaded on August 6, 2015.
- Sonneratia alba* - Protabase Record. http://database.prota.org/PROTAhtml/Sonneratia%20alba_En.htm. Downloaded on August 22, 2015.
- Sonneratia alba* - The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. <http://www.iucnredlist.org/details/178804/0>. Downloaded on August 22, 2015.
- Sonneratia alba* - Mangroves of Singapore. <http://mangrove.nus.edu.sg/guidebooks/text/1073.htm>. Downloaded on August 22, 2015.
- Harizon BP, Dikdik K, Dadan S, Yoshihito S, Unang S. Antibacterial triterpenoids from the bark of *Sonneratia alba* (Lythraceae). *Nat Prod Commun* 2015; 10(2):277–80.
- Wada K, Kinjo A, Uehara M, Takara K, 2002. Antioxidant activities of mangrove trees. *Sci Links Jpn* 189–192.
- Nuntavan B, Aranya J, Prapinsara S, Wiroj T, Sanit A, Harry H, Fong S, Pezzuto MJ, Jerry K. Pharmacological studies of plants in the mangrove forest. *Thai J Phytophar* 2003; 10:1–12.
- Harizon, Pujiastuti B, Kurnia D, Sumiarsa D, dan Shiono Y. Triterpenoid lupan darikulit batang *Sonneratia alba* (Lythraceae). *Bionatura-Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Hayatidan Fisik*. 2014; 16(1):43–47.
- Thu NTH, Khánh LP, Duy NT, Chánh NTK, Phùng NKP, Hansen PE. Chemical constituents from leaves of *Sonneratia alba* J.E. Smith (Sonneratiaceae). *J Sci Tech Dev* 2011; 14: 6.
- Asad S, Hamiduzzaman Md, Zafrul Azam ATM, Ahsan M, Masud MM. Lupeol, oleanic acid & steroids from *Sonneratia alba* J.E. Sm. (Sonneratiaceae) and antioxidant, antibacterial & cytotoxic activities of its extracts. *Int J Adv Res Pharm Bio Sci* 2013; 3(4):1–10.
- Chaiyadej K, Wongthap H, Vadhanavikit S, Chantrapromma K. Bioactive constituents from the twigs of *Sonneratia alba*. *Walailak J Sci & Tech* 2004; 1(1):15–22.
- Herawati N, Firdaus. 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic acid, an antioxidant phenolics compound from *Sonneratia alba* bark. *Jurnal Natur Indonesia* 2013; 15(1): 63–67.
- Patil Priya D, Chavan Niranjana S, Sabale AB. *Sonneratia alba* J. Smith: a vital source of gamma linolenic acid (GLA). *Asian J Pharm Clin Res* 2012; 5(Suppl. 1):172–175.
- Onoja E, Ndukwe IG. Isolation of oleanolic acid from chloroform extract of *Borreria stachydea* [(DC) Hutch. and Dalziel]. *J. Nat. Prod. Plant Resour.* 2013; 3 (2):57–60.
- J Hussain, F Ullah, H Hussain, ST Hussain, MR Shah. Nepetolide: A New Diterpene from *Nepeta suaveis*. *Z. Naturforsch.* 2008; 63b:591–594.
- Akihisa T, Kojima N, Kikuchi T, Yasukawa K, Tokuda H, Masters ET, Manosroi A, Manosroi J. Anti-inflammatory and chemopreventive effects of triterpene cinnamates and acetates from shea fat. *J Oleo Sci* 2010; 59(6):273-280.
- Awad AB, Chinnman M, Fink CS, Bradford PG. β -Sitosterol activates Fas signaling in human breast cancer cells. *Phytomed* 2007; 14:747–754.
- R Pandey, R Kaur, R Malasoni & M M Gupta. Lupeol ester from *Clerodendrum phlomidis* L. *Indian J Chem.* 2008; 47B:470-472.
- Ragasa CY, Caro JL, Shen C-C. Triterpenes and sterol from *Artocarpus ovatus*. *J Appl Pharm Sci* 2014; 4(10):7-11.
- Ragasa CY, Ng VAS, Ebajo Jr V, Fortin D, De Los Reyes MM, Shen C-C. Triterpenes from *Shorea negrosensis*. *Der Pharmacia Lettre* 2014; 6(6):453-458.
- Ng VAS, Agoos EM, Shen C-C, Ragasa CY. Chemical constituents of *Cycas sancti-lasallei*. *J Appl Pharm Sci* 2015; 5(Suppl. 1):12-17.
- Ragasa CY, Ng VAS, De Los Reyes MM, Mandia EH, Oyong GG, Shen C-C. Chemical constituents and cytotoxicity of the leaves of *Dysoxylum gaudichaudianum* (A. Juss.) Miq. *Der Pharma Chemica* 2014, 6(5):182-187.
- Zhang M and Shen Y. The anti-cancer effects of ursolic acid and oleanolic acid in the digestive system, A Review. *Shanghai Yiyao* 2011; 32(12):606-611.
- Oguro T, Liu J, Klaassen CD, Yoshida T. Inhibitory effect of oleanolic acid on 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate-induced gene expression in mouse skin. *Toxicol Sci* 1998; 45:88–93.
- Li J, Guo W-J, Yang Q-Y. Effects of ursolic acid and oleanolic acid on human colon carcinoma cell line HCT15. *World J Gastroenterol* 2002; 8(3):493–495.
- Liu J, Wu N, Ma L, Liu M, Liu G, Zhang Y. Oleanolic acid suppresses aerobic glycolysis in cancer cells by switching pyruvate kinase Type M isoforms. *PLoS ONE* 2014; 9(3): e91606. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0091606.
- Neto CC (2011). Ursolic acid and other pentacyclic triterpenoids anticancer activities and occurrence in

- berries. In: Berries and Cancer Prevention, Stoner GD and Seeram NP (Eds.). Springer Science+Business Media, LLC:41-49.
29. Wang X, Zhang F, Yang L, Mei Y, Long H, Zhang X, Zhang J, Su Q-S. Ursolic acid inhibits proliferation and induces apoptosis of cancer cells *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *J Biomed Biotechnol* 2011; Article ID 419343, 8 pages.
 30. Wang W, Zhao C, Jou D, Lu J, Zhang C, Lin L, Lin J. Ursolic acid inhibits the growth of colon cancer-initiating cells by targeting STAT3. *Anticancer Res* 2013; 33(10):4279-4284.
 31. Kim H-I, Quan F-S, Kim J-E, Lee N-R, Kim HJ, Jo SJ. Inhibition of estrogen signaling through depletion of estrogen receptor alpha by ursolic acid and betulinic acid from *Prunella vulgaris* var. *lilacina*. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 2014; 451(2):282-287.
 32. Kassi E, Papoutsis Z, Pratsinis H, Aliannis N, Manoussakis, Moutsatsou P. Ursolic acid, a naturally occurring triterpenoid, demonstrates anticancer activity on human prostate cancer cells. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol* 2007; 133:493-500.
 33. Kaewthawee N, Brimson S. The effects of ursolic acid on cytokine production via the MPKA pathways in leukemic T-cells. *EXCLI J* 2013; 12:102-114.
 34. Leng S, Hao Y, Du D, Xie S, Hong L, Gu H, Zhu X, Zhang J, Fan D, Kung H-F. Ursolic acid promotes cancer cell death by inducing Atg5-dependent autophagy. *Int J Cancer* 2013; 133(12):2781-2790.
 35. Shen S, Zhang Y, Zhang R, Tu X, Gong X. Ursolic acid induces autophagy in U87MG cells via ROS-dependent endoplasmic reticulum stress. *Chemico-Biol Interact* 2014; 218:28-41.
 36. Awad AB, Chinnman M, Fink CS, Bradford PG. β -Sitosterol activates Fas signaling in human breast cancer cells. *Phytomed* 2007; 14:747-754.
 37. Jayaprakasha GK, Mandadi KK, Poulouse SM, Jadegoud Y, Gowda GA, Patil BS. Inhibition of colon cancer growth and antioxidant activity of bioactive compounds from *Poncirus trifoliata* (L.) Raf. *Bioorg Med Chem* 2007; 15:4923-4932.
 38. Baskar AA, Ignacimuthu S, Paulraj G, Numair K. Chemopreventive potential of β -sitosterol in experimental colon cancer model-an *in vitro* and *in vivo* study. *BMC Comp Alt Med* 2010; 10:24.
 39. Jesch ED, Seo JM, Carr TP, Lee JY. Sitosterol reduces messenger RNA and protein expression levels of Niemann-Pick C1-like 1 in FHs 74 Int cells. *Nutr Res* 2009; 29(12):859-66.
 40. Moon DO, Kyeong Jun L, Yung HC, Gi-Young K. *Int Immunopharmacol* 2007; 7:1044-1053.
 41. Ghosh T, Maity TK, Singh J. Evaluation of antitumor activity of stigmaterol, a constituent isolated from *Bacopa monnieri* Linn aerial parts against ehrlich ascites carcinoma in mice. *Orient Pharm Exp Med* 2011; 11:41-49.
 42. Batta AK, Xu G, Honda A, Miyazaki T, Salen G. Stigmaterol reduces plasma cholesterol levels and inhibits hepatic synthesis and intestinal absorption in the rat. *Metabolism* 2006; 55(3):292-299.
 43. Gómez MA, García MD, Sáenz MT. Cytostatic activity of *Achillea ageratum* L. *Phytother Res* 2001; 15(7):633-634.
 44. Kasahara Y, Kumaki K, Katagiri S, Yasukawa K, Yamanouchi S, Takido M. Carthami flos extract and its component, stigmaterol, inhibit tumour promotion in mouse skin two-stage carcinogenesis. *Phytother Res* 1994; 8(6):327-331.
 45. Lim J-C, Park JH, Budesinsky M, Kasal A, Han Y-H, Koo B-S, Lee S-I, Lee D-U. Antimutagenic constituents from the thorns of *Gleditsia sinensis*. *Chem Pharm Bull* 2005; 53(5):561-564.
 46. García MD, Sáenz MT, Gómez MA, Fernández MA. Topical anti-inflammatory activity of phytosterols isolated from *Eryngium foetidum* on chronic and acute inflammation models. *Phytother Res* 1999; 13(1):78-80.
 47. Gabay O, Sanchez C, Salvat C, Chevy F, Breton M, Nourissat G. Stigmaterol: a phytosterol with potential anti-osteoarthritic properties. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 2010; 18(1):106-116.
 48. Panda S, Jafri M, Kar A, Meheta BK. Thyroid inhibitory, antiperoxidative and hypoglycemic effects of stigmaterol, isolated from *Butea monosperma*. *Fitoter* 2009; 80(2):123-126.
 49. Prachayasittikul S, Saraban P, Cherdtrakulkiat R, Ruchirawat S. Prachayasittikul V. New bioactive triterpenoids and antimalarial activity of *Diospyros rubra* Lec. *Excli J* 2010; 9:1-10.
 50. Vidya L, Leni M, Varalakshmi P. Evaluation of the effect of triterpenes on urinary risk factors of stone formation in pyridoxine hyperoxaluric rats. *Phytother Res* 2002; 16 (6):514-518.
 51. Anand R, Patnaik GK, Kulshreshtha DK, Dhawan N. Antiuro lithiatic activity of lupeol, the active constituent of *Crateva nuriala*. *Phytother Res* 1994; 8(7):417-421.
 52. Rao CV, Mark HLN, Reddy BS. Chemopreventive effect of squalene on colon cancer. *Carcinogenesis* 1998; 19:287-290.
 53. Farvin KHS, Anandan R, Hari S, Kumar S, Shing KS, Mathew S, Sankar TV, Nair PGV. Cardioprotective effect of squalene on lipid profile in isoprenaline-induced myocardial infarction in rats. *J Med Food* 2006; 9(4):531-536.
 54. Loganathan R, Selvaduray KR, Nesaretnam K, Radhakrisnan A. Differential and antagonistic effects of palm tocotrienols and other phytonutrients (carotenoids, squalene and coenzyme Q10) on breast cancer cells *in vitro*. *J Oil Palm Res* 2013; 25:208-215.
 55. Desai KN, Wei H, Lamartiniere CA. The preventive and therapeutic potential of the squalene-containing compound, Roindex, on tumor promotion and regression. *Cancer Lett* 1996; 101:93-96.
 56. Ronco AL, De Stéfani E. Squalene: a multi-task link in the crossroads of cancer and aging. *Functional Foods in Health and Disease* 2013; 3:462-476.